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A TYPIFICATION OF THE ORGANIZED CRIME WEAPONS TRAFFIC AND ITS RELATIONS WITH THE RIO DE JANEIRO STATE SECURITY SYSTEM

Sabrina Medeiros

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4954-3623>

André Leiras

**Specialist in Public Security
Police Officer, Rio de Janeiro**

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Summary

The repercussions of violence in Rio de Janeiro are visible and known, but studies on the nature of this violence are still few. Most of these studies focused on social and political-historical conditioners considered the impact of social and development structures on the conflict and violence degrees (Shyne 2010; Misse 2007). In addition to studies associated with violence as a result of the social instability of Rio de Janeiro, it is also essential to observe the organizational aspects of crime, concerning the logistics chains and suppliers, mainly because this is an aspect that is necessary for the maintenance of profitability and stability of the system of the illicit economy.

Thus, Rio de Janeiro ceases to be only a consumer and becomes a supplier of other types of crime, offering an essential group of weapons to various organizations and groups focused, for example, on the theft of cargo vehicles, among others. There is no doubt that the state of violence in this state of the federation is primarily associated with the possession of high caliber weapons by criminal organizations and their members. That part of the territory also suffers from the precarious care of citizens by the institutions because of the limitations that the areas occupied by criminal factions provoke, from the possession of high lethal power weaponry.

In this context, this policy brief presents the context of crime in Rio de Janeiro, which deals with a large volume of weaponry of high lethality, and the objectives outlined for the typification of weapons in the illegal economy of Rio de Janeiro. The Rio de Janeiro case may offer insights to other phenomena where gun traffic is a function of other types of crime. The case study (Yin 1997; Masud 2018) is the method chosen to detect the seizure experience of DESARME police station to give conditions to observe a more general phenomenon that illustrates the field of arms trafficking, its components, and, finally, the results for public security. Thus, from the case study of the work of the DESARME civil police station in the first two years of its establishing by the government of Rio de Janeiro, between 2017 and 2018, we detect the purchasing preference model that is in progress, the most relevant variables that characterize the subsystem of arms trafficking, the origins, and possible viable routes to feed this system of illegality.

Thus, the inductive method benefits this study from original interviews and databases are organized according to research interests, from primary data provided by the public security system of Rio de Janeiro. The interviews used in this study were conducted individually, as well as the questions are mainly assembled according to the area of specialty and experience of the interviewees. There were eight interview respondents between agents (inspectors) of DESARME, the specialized police station established for few years, and inspectors linked to the

purchasing and seizure control systems.

In addition, a questionnaire was sent to a group of high-level officials of the Rio de Janeiro Public Security Secretary (extinguished in 2019), which sought to detect impressions about the weapons system of organized crime, as well as its relationship with that of the police. As for the primary data, some are those produced by the Institute of Public Security or from DESARME, which is the focus of this work. The weapons and military mean that matter to the study is those used in combat, especially the weapons and ammunition used, of operational solid appeal. The variables considered are those as follows: the origin of the armament in terms of company and country, the routes and volume of material, and the repercussions on the other types of crimes.

Finally, this study seeks to give visibility to certain elements and analyses that are limited, contributing with insights also derived from unpublished data.

Background

The dynamics of the arms trade and the culture of violence have already been the subject of study (Briceño-León and Zubillaga 2012; Stohl and Schroeder 2007; Silva et al. 2018, Shine 2010, Nagle 2002). This study focuses on the relationship between the illegal arms trade and violence by criminal organizations, seeking to list a group of types that reveal part of the economic nature of violence affecting the case of Rio de Janeiro through the model of purchases in force. The repercussions of the economy of illicit - crimes considered adjacent to drug trafficking, such as the theft of ATMs, vehicles, and the theft of cargo (Silva et al. 2018, p.8-9) – are conditioned by the arms' trafficking, guaranteeing it permanent sustainability.

Cargo theft is among the most affected types of crime conditioned by arms trafficking. Since this is an economy of direct impact on the current commercial system, an unsuccessful public security policy results in a progressive decrease in interest in private capital investment in commercial and industrial facilities and the trade that feeds the installed sectors. The pressure of companies affected by the increasing crime of cargo theft focuses on the prices charged, promoted by the scarcity of products and the increase in the insurance of the cargo.

The specialization of criminal organizations in the theft of cargo was pointed out by Silva et al. (2018), who argue, citing the data offered by the Institute of Public Security of the state of Rio de Janeiro (ISP) that this type of crime has increased the crime firepower to consequently increase the results associated with the profitability of these actions. Field research was done by the authors, contributing to detecting Rio de Janeiro as in the first place of the ranking of crime attacks on cargo

transportation in Brazil. This type of crime includes high profitability and a bottleneck of the leading logistics routes of supply chain service. For Silva et al. (2018), the logistic stifling could be mitigated by creating other models and the expansion of logistics channels. In addition, the authors pointed to the need for more police staff, a more severe penalty to criminals, and the control of other logistic modals to contain crime in the sector.

In this sense, the need for re-rigging police institutions indicates the demand for instruments compatible with their respective functions. Despite the need for technology and integrated information systems concerning the investigative roles, the demand for weaponry parity may put the police, conversely, under increasing militarization, as the armed forces and urban security interventions had contributed in the last years (Håndlykken-Luz 2020; Rodrigues 2012). On the other hand, militarization seems to be a characteristic attributed to the police when the degree of lethality of their actions is considered high, linked to the ability to generate civilian damage in police operations. The prominent stigma of the militarization process is the associated civilian cost, which is commonly dissociated from the risks and costs for the police. More recently, a defense noisily focused on the issue of police vulnerability in the face of the militarization of criminal organizations appears in public opinion (Kinsella 2006; 2014).

Thus, the context of high lethality between police and civilians in a structure reinforced by combat and confrontation ends up offering an actual weight to armament as a conditioning factor of violence, both from the perspective of criminal activity and how the police act. Otherwise, disadvantaged by consistent and long-term public policies, the Rio de Janeiro police have suffered disrepair, making them more vulnerable to the lethality cycle. One explanation for this is that the system's weapons were seized in a circumstantial, emergency, and unplanned manner. Thus, the cycles are supported by contingency actions in which the imperative of planning is abandoned while criminal organizations' illegal access to weapons develops. Here seems to lie the central point of the sustainability of organized crime, the high power of violence and lethality, and, in these circumstances, the unpreparedness and injury of the police forces in response.

Considering the internationalization of crime in the face of the globalization of economies (Briceño-León and Zubillaga 2002; Trim 2017; UN Report), the ongoing changes in the drug economy are relevant, especially with new forms of distribution and drug production, with less accessibility and an important cyber-dimension. The issue of illegality also benefits from systematic internet network access to foreign markets that both enable chemical materials transferring, such as partitions and weaponry. In addition, an essential asset of this economic subsystem is the illicit flow of capital, which allows renewed and low-traceable payment systems. The flow of knowledge is also essential. From the availability of techniques previously not accessible to the knowledge for weapons operation to the techniques of equipment

adaptation, automation of weapons, and creation of human resources as gunsmiths, all, are part of this illegal subsystem.

The imperative that moves the arms' trafficking system is tied to the high-profit margin that drug trafficking allows and, until a few decades ago, represented a subsidiary economy to the leading economy of illicit drugs. With the enrichment of the drug trafficking business and its specialties over the years – such as the preference for cocaine and synthetic drugs (less bulky and more profitable than marijuana, for example), actions that were previously logistical or subsidiary, such as the possession of weapons for the security of the business, gained prominence. This is because this economy began to have its impact on the illegal economy of criminal organizations, which also organized themselves progressively around this business, as mediators, service providers, and as guarantors of the system of territorial occupation that was on the communities most affected by the distribution and sale of drugs.

The Rio de Janeiro police procurement system was subject to political party cyclothymia, as was most of the ongoing public policies at the federative level. On the other hand, the economy of illegality is not a relevant factor for the long-term planning of acquisitions in public security since there is no system in operation that is tied to the economy of arms trafficking on the same scale (Kinsella 2017).

Access to weapons has been the subject of great repercussion for civil conflicts of different natures, both in African countries and in urban areas of South and Central America. One of the main challenges regarding the containment of illegal arms trafficking is the cooperation regarding the information network that runs from the local to the federal levels, permitting some degree of international awareness of the types and origins of illegal weapons. United Nations efforts through the Department of Drugs and Crime (UNODC) have given visibility to the associated challenges in Africa, especially after the conflicts in Libya (2011) and Mali (2012), with a high incidence of illegal weapons circulation.

The UN and agencies have developed different approaches and instruments related to the illegal arms trafficking and crime frameworks. Similarly, other instruments aimed at forming more participatory public policies have significant scope in the matter. Finally, with the recent appreciation of studies on practices, which have been called "practice turn" (Buerger 2018: p. 13), there is an increasing interest in how public policies affect their various faces linked to micro-processes, believing that the incidence, in reality, can start from micro-processes in the benefit of significant macro purposes, with a greater chance of being responsive. Thus, the on-site observation of the work carried out by an agency of the complex of institutions that are part of the public system of security governance can illustrate and offer insights not achieved, either by the visibility of data or by the experimentation of the theme under another political spectrum.

Findings

The relationship between the reduction of arms trafficking and the increase in the cost of dealing with it had been signaled by Michel Misse (2007, p. 156). That is, although the relationship between violence and the narco-economy in Rio de Janeiro is significant, the issue of arms trafficking and implications for the success or failure of public security policies had been little addressed.

In addition to the relationship among different business types, where drugs and weapons complement a complex system that benefits from both, other crimes such as cargo theft are little explored (Cardoso and Silva 2018; Vieira 2016). The economic subsystems generated by illicit activities include the weapons rental system, from where weapons are marked with identities such as CX and are also part of the financial complex that supplies organizations, hierarchy and creates organicity (Shelley 2018; Stohl 2007). Innovations are also part of the culture that is expressed in this type of illegality: organizations form their gunsmiths who, given the circulation of technical information with a higher proportion, end up being essential agents, since they guarantee innovative processes such as the automation of weapons and cartridges coupled with large amounts of ammunition.

Gun seizures in recent years and Rio de Janeiro have a vital component, and that has no parity: the specialized police station DESARME, created in 2017 by the then Secretary of Public Security Roberto Sá, to absorb and qualify investigations associated with the crime of arms trafficking in a specialized and unique way in the history of public security in Rio de Janeiro. According to the deputy operational chief of the Civil Police at the time:

"Desarme is a strategic action of SESEG and the Police Chief of enormous value, and that will certainly bring excellent results for security policy and combating crime in the state (...) The work methodology to be implemented in the specialized police station has as its central pillar intelligence and integration actions".

Although the project had been implemented within the integration dynamics that the City of Police provides - a dedicated site to various police stations as an enterprise that included narcotics to cybercrimes -the project still lacked to ensure integration and cooperation between the police stations other agencies. The level of integration was also restricted to the relationships and personal initiatives of some delegates and officials so that the protocols do not represent a highly efficient mechanism for the interaction and exchange of information aimed at combating crime.

During the years in question, DESARME reached high rates of seizures and processes related to arms trafficking, enabling the analysis of results not only by the scope of the difference in terms of the numbers achieved but by the creation of an informational ally associated with a typification that was not evident before. The DESARME project is explained in a document called "Multidirectional Partner in Investigative Police Work," which was used in this work as a primary source, registering integrated actions and interagency cooperation through DESARME as the driving factor. Still, data analysis in a systematic and specialized manner is also hampered by the high political variability over technical frameworks, which are not achieved by an efficient long-term human resources policy.

Thus, an important point to be highlighted is the issue of police technical staff and the complete change of frameworks conditioned to political mandates. Except for positions such as police expert, which are highly specialized and defined, the inspector and delegate boards vary when changing police leadership, losing the continuity of processes as happens in the political sphere, although with human resources originally formed by public competitions. In this sense, the lack of permanence in the police of specialized human resources projects is also a liability of this public policy. That directly interferes in the fight against crimes such as arms trafficking, creating vulnerabilities to the investigation processes.

As for the interviews conducted, some diagnoses can be made. Until a few years ago (the 1980s and 1990s), the weapons were the 12-gauge shotgun, machine guns or submachine guns 45, revolver 38, and pistol 45. Police acquisitions of weapons and PPE (Personal Protective Equipment) as vests were also correspondingly less complex: machine guns, 12-gauge rifles, and a few obsolete rifles used in wars for decades. After that (end of the 1990s), the first rifles of the AR platform and AK platform were identified, in addition to those of the FAO and G3 platform, imported through the borders of Argentina and Bolivia. The police began buying equivalent rifles, but Taurus's acquisition monopoly forced the police to buy the manufacturer's pistols of inferior technical quality. The vests also purchased were not suitable for protection, so the police made the acquisition of inferior quality material without equivalence to the material used by criminal organizations. This situation has progressively deteriorated further.

From 2012 on, there has been a significant and systematic entry of new weaponry into increasingly organized crime. Information systems, weapons, and PPEs quickly became obsolete. The quality of the ammunition used was also far behind due to the same conditions, mainly because the ammunition is still a monopoly of the Brazilian Cartridge Company (CBC). The police in Rio de Janeiro were forced to modernize, which was done since 2015, from when the monopoly of Brazilian companies was broken regarding the purchase of weapons (according to an interview with an inspector, November 2018). The issue of monopoly affects the issue of the quality of the purchased material, and the legislation of control of lots - huge batches of

ammunition, marked for destination control - also impairs this confrontation and parity.

The seizures by DESARME in the period equivalent to this study point to 79% of foreign weapons, as shown on the first chart above, which qualifies the problem and complexity of arms trafficking in Rio de Janeiro as a predominantly international nature.

The second chart points to the typification of weapons, recording that the weapons used in urban areas in Rio de Janeiro are light weapons (81%) and rifles (19%). Despite the institutional weaknesses pointed out in all interviews conducted to detect the field of the illegal weapons system, especially those associated with the career system, merit, and long-term policies, the results revealed from the creation of DESARME are relevant for the first mapping of this market. The detected variables that configure a component type of this typification are essential.

Among the variables chosen for the typification of the illegal weapons system in operation in Rio de Janeiro, we list:

- Internationality (versus national weapons).
- Type of weapon (models and calibers).
- Trafficking route (from the origin of the purchase).

These data suggest that arms trafficking directed to Rio de Janeiro has an international expression and guarantees drug trafficking and other illicit trade, precisely because its sustainability is in territorial occupation, in the domain of communities and trade posts. The permeability of borders seems to be the first element to be detected when the data on weapons seizures in Rio de Janeiro is observed between 2017 and 2018. Despite the efforts associated with creating warning, registration, and alert bases among Interpol members, the

operationalization between unique federative systems and the international systematization still centralized in the Federal Police do not contribute to the efficient operation of data between agencies and distinct attributions.

Otherwise, the typification of the weapons used by these organizations demonstrates another side of this model: the majority use of pistols, which represents the ease of their use and transit; and the use in a large proportion of rifles, permanently used for the purpose of ensuring illicit traffic and as a source of ostentatious territorial dominance.

These two distinct uses reach different spectra from the model of purchase of weapons used, even if in order to explore the windows of opportunity of illegality routes. The first aspect is associated with common crimes. The use of weapons considered light as pistols does not guarantee that lethality is also light. Especially with the automation process and greater efficiency of pistols, the lethality achieved has been represented. Otherwise, the use of rifles empowers the most sensitive sphere of crimes inactivity in Rio de Janeiro: the dominance of territories occupied by criminal organizations and, secondarily, an arsenal of war that enables them to commit other crimes of more significant proportion such as cargo thefts, or wars between factions or against police forces or armed forces that challenge this territorial occupation.

Along with the issue of trafficking and possession of weapons for the benefit of organized crime is the sustainability of organizations, also associated with the possession of ammunition. The seizure of ammunition points in the direction of internationalization but reveals something else. The fragility of the regulation on the lots of ammunition reveals that a significant part of the ammunition is national, which points to the uncontrol of state purchases or deviations about the manufacture and distribution of national ammunition. In the case of the murder of Rio

de Janeiro Council representative Marielle Franco and her driver, Anderson Gomes, the ammunition was part of Lot UZZ-18, which was sold to the Federal Police in 2006 by the Brazilian Cartridge Company. The Lot was predicted in 2 million capsules, which is much less controllable to the destinations of the ammunition. Currently, an ordinance of the Brazilian Army defines how this marking of ammunition control should be made, but there is still no relevant legislation. Similarly, the presence of Russia as a third actor in this statistic is also a relevant indication of the creation of alternatives for supply other than the countries of the Americas and Europe, commonly associated with routes to Brazil.

A relevant fact is that the origin of the armament and/or ammunition cannot always be tied to the country of origin. One of the most critical weapons for the illegal arms trafficking is Glock pistols of Austrian origin. However, as can be seen in the chart below, some imports to the United States may be responsible for diverting routes that serve Rio de Janeiro, so the factories in the United States are also part of these possible paths.

Recently, in the context of foreign relations that is affecting the issue of the sale and resale of weapons and ammunition, the US pressured Paraguay on the sale of arms to this country on account of the that specific weapons and ammunition were identified in other poles of civil crisis and illicit use of these same weapons. This indicator may have reduced the entry into Brazil of this same type of weaponry purchased by the Paraguayan state and finally diverted to illicit routes that reach Rio de Janeiro.

Finally, a questionnaire was made to amplify the vision of the practitioners in addition to the interviews with agents directly linked to DESARME and the structure of purchases and seizure of weapons. "Logistics and Ammunition Purchase Facility" and "Purchase by Opportunity" were the main elements characterized as the determinant for the purchases by organized crime. For them, the lack of supervision in ports, airports, highways, and land borders is the cause of the cycle of arms trafficking that creates the cycle of violence in which Rio de Janeiro is located.

A second point highlighted is that Rio de Janeiro uses weapons as an object of maintaining arms trafficking, but the organized crime of Rio de Janeiro is an integral part of the arms trafficking route as a business itself. 91.8% of the respondents indicated that it is possible to perceive a weapons' purchasing system characterized by explicit preferences, where rifles of foreign origin are the main product (89.3%).

They also note an increase in the military capacity of organized crime so that 83.7% of respondents believe that the police do not have the weapons system (weapons and PPE) necessary for ostentatious combat. Last, 73.5% of respondents also believe that the police's gun purchase system should consider the crime procurement system.

Otherwise, the solutions to the end of this cycle do not seem to be in the police purchasing system since the cycle is exponential violence. Thus, the fight against routes and arms trafficking involves mainly control surveillance, despite recognizing the tactical-operational disadvantage when considering weapons purchasing systems in the police institutions.

Conclusions

We should consider that efforts to map the origin and destiny of illegal arms should consider international organizations and local institutions such as specialized crime police stations. There are no official channels, by now, to flow this information towards federal or international institutions from the federative police instances. The Norwegian Initiative on Small Arms Transfers has been congregating data on small arms transfer by a collaborative initiative, but since the end of 2017, due to a lack of funding, it is no longer being updated.

The Peace Research Institute Oslo (PRIO) and Igarapé Institute initiative called MAD (Mapping Arms Data) is not updated since 2014, but data show an increase of imports from 1994 to 2014 of more than eight times (around 4 million to 31 million small arms imported) (PRIO, Igarapé 2014). It should be noted that those projects count on official channels of transferring, and not the illegal arms flows, which should be considered from estimative derived chiefly from the arms and munitions apprehensions.

As can be seen, the implications for public security of this typology presented are of various orders. For state procurement planning, where the imperative is that of long-term symmetrical and proportional planning, or for planning with the state's ability to combat drug trafficking, typifying the weapons system of criminal organizations is necessary and directly affects the efficiency of the public security system and its ability to fight crime.

Thus, for federative and national integration in public security, the material produced by DESARME points to the need for data systematization in congruence with Brazil and international intelligence systems to be classified as the operational and intelligence capacity for the proportion of the ambiance that the illegality of arms trafficking sustains. The study's main conclusion points to a system of reception of

weapons from abroad provided by the increased permeability of maritime and land borders and lack of control of the entrance checkpoints. It also points to a modernized system of organized crime purchases, which has seen a significant increase in lethality over the past ten years. At the same time, the disparity of weapons seems to be a factor of disincentive and police lethality, but it does not seem to be the solution to address the issue, which involves border control and illegal trafficking.

Recommendations

In order to offer conclusions that can contribute to the analysis of the topic, it was possible to diagnose that the combination of some factors is determinant for a successful public policy regarding arms trafficking and that this type of crime is a support of the lethality and degree of intensity of violence affecting public security in Rio de Janeiro.

First, it weighs the need for its legal regulation of weapons, as to the controls of import and legal production, regarding the possession of heavy weapons of illegal origin, which also finds no place in criminal legislation and associated punishment system. Regulations on arms, in addition, the signing of protocols and sustainable actions for the benefit of integrated security and interagency cooperation seems to be decisive since investigative, intelligence, and combat work depend on a complex structure of actions against networked and highly profitable crimes. Finally, a long-term human resources policy, with the modernization of the structure in a recurrent way, assists the DESARME project in the continuity item, which seems indispensable such as the complexity of actions that challenge the national architecture to combat organized crime.

During the Covid-19 pandemic period (2020-recent), controlling illegal flows was more challenging and data aggregation even more difficult. This study was made until the Federal Intervention on the Rio de Janeiro Public Security system, during the federal government of Michel Temer (2016-2018).

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Interviews:
Criminal Expert - head of the Carlos Eboli Institute of Criminalistics (ICCE) research expertise sector.

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<https://interagency.institute/>
contact@interagency.institute
